

SPARC Connectivity Knowledge base of the Autonomic Nervous System (SCKAN) Curation Manual

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Natural language processing (NLP)-based Pipeline and Curation Guide

Goal: To leverage the results from reviewing statements extracted from biomedical literature, textbooks, and expert input to generate knowledge about the autonomic nervous system (ANS) and its related connections in a format suitable for import into the SPARC Autonomic Nervous System Connectivity Knowledge Base (SCKAN). This guide serves as a curation manual, outlining the workflow and criteria for curators when building neuronal populations.

SPARC Portal: <https://sparc.science/>

About SCKAN: <https://sparc.science/tools-and-resources/6eg3VpJbwQR4B84CjrvmyD>

Latest SCKAN Release: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5337441>

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F T Imam et al., (2024) biorxiv
<https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.10.25.620360>

Overview of the SCKAN Curation Workflow

Neuron Population Curation			
TRIAGE	1	Monthly NLP screening of literature	
	2	Import into OSCAP	
	3		
	4		
	5	OSCAP status updated	
DISTILL	6		
	7		
	8		
	9	OSCAP status update	
ENGINEER	10		
	11		
	12		
	13		
	14		
	15	OSCAP status update	

Communication by email

Work done on spreadsheets

Work done using software tools

Overview of the SCKAN Curation Workflow

Overview of SCKAN Curation Workflow

An NLP-based pipeline was developed to identify papers in the scientific literature containing connectivity information (Ozyurt et al., 2021). The NLP-based pipeline is run monthly on new full length PMC open access articles. These new publications can either be articles published since the last run or older articles whose full texts have recently become available.

Extracted connectivity sentences are imported into OSCAP (The Open SAWG Connectivity Authoring Pipeline). The content is reviewed by the triage operator to determine whether it is within scope and whether there is new connectivity information that needs to be added to SCKAN. The rationale behind the triage process is shown in slide 8. If there are any content-related questions, the triage operator consults with the SPARC Anatomical Working Group (SAWG). Out-of-scope content is flagged, and the feedback is used to update the NLP-based pipeline algorithm.

Relevant sentences/papers are then checked against the connections already present in SCKAN. Each sentence is flagged accordingly, and the curator adds the connection, usually by tracking down additional references. Existing connections in SCKAN can be enriched if additional information is available in other species or if contradictory findings are identified.

The curator uses the NLP-extracted content and additional references to draft relevant neuronal connections. Once this process is completed, the curator presents the connections to the SAWG group or an anatomical expert in the field (e.g., if the connections are organ-focused, an expert in that field may be consulted) to review the evidence, provide anatomical expertise, and ultimately decide whether the connections should be added to SCKAN. Connections that are not approved can be revised or rejected. Additionally, connections can be flagged with an alert explaining any concerns about the nature of the evidence.

Overview of SCKAN Curation Workflow

Each connectivity statement models the connection of a single neuronal population and follows the format below. This format is also the most efficient way for domain experts to review the proposed connections when distilled into a single sentence:

Region A to Region B via Nerve C

Where:

- Region A = origin of projection
- Region B = target of projection (may be more than one region)
- Nerve C = nerve conveying projections. May be multiple branches.

SCKAN models a theoretical neuron population that subserves this connection, such that:

- Region(s) A = location of somata
- Region(s) B = location of axon terminals
- Nerve(s) C = location or locations of axons

Neuron Population **N** at **A** projects to **B** via C (X, Y, Z)
where A, B, and C represent Anatomical locations

- N **hasSomaLocation** A
- N **hasAxonTerminalLocation** B
- N **hasAxonLocation** C

Overview of SCKAN Curation Workflow

The structure of the connectivity statement facilitates collaboration between curators and knowledge engineers, as it directly maps onto the underlying data model of SCKAN. Additionally, the way connections are drafted enhances the review process and allows for the addition of notes and alerts on specific components of the connectivity statement (e.g., “B”).

Once the review process is completed and both parties (curator and domain experts) agree on the neuron populations to be added, the curator encodes the neuronal populations in NPO format to streamline the handoff to the knowledge engineer. This process, outlined below in slides 12-15, represents the population based on:

- (i) the anatomical location of the soma,
- (ii) axon segments and terminals,
- (iii) the association of anatomical locations with phenotype identifiers (such as UBERON or InterLex), and
- (iv) species and sex details.

Each connectivity statement includes provenance information specifying its source, which may originate from scientific literature, textbooks, and/or expert knowledge. These sources are linked to their respective identifiers, including DOI or PMID for research articles, ISBN for books, and ORCID for expert contributions. Additionally, curators may append notes and alerts to any population entry to provide further context.

Triage procedure tree

This is the triage process followed for every sentence extracted from the NLP-based pipeline (Ozyurt et al., 2021).

Triage process: Tags for sentences

Tags enable efficient sorting, prevent redundancy, and facilitate multi-project use. They improve searchability, ensure consistency, and streamline knowledge integration by categorizing extracted sentences based on themes, relevance, and metadata. A structured tagging system prevents duplicate work and enhances interoperability across different initiatives.

Pros of Using Tags in Triage

- ✓ **Efficient Organization** – Quickly sort and retrieve relevant content.
- ✓ **Prevents Redundancy** – Avoids duplicate work across projects.
- ✓ **Standardization** – Ensures consistency in data curation.
- ✓ **Better Knowledge Integration** – Aligns with ontologies and structured vocabularies.

- It is worthwhile tagging good articles for future use of content to expand SCKAN. Right now tags can only be added to the comments. Please differentiate them using brackets for ease of search [tag]:
 - [Molecular]: Contains molecular information about a connection, e.g., receptors, neurotransmitters
 - [Sensory]: Sensory peripheral connection
 - [Vagus]: Vagus nerve and branches anatomy
 - [Cell]: Contains information about cell types
 - [Synaptic]: Direct synaptic connectivity asserted
- [SAWG]: Flag for SAWG.
- [Reflex]: Note papers about autonomic reflexes that may be considered for ApiNATOMY.
- [Clinical] Data in humans.
- Additional specific tags to be used [Sentence Triaging Tags](#).

Overview of distillation process

- Distillation is the process of creating neuron populations extracted from scientific articles, textbooks and expert input.
- Currently this process discussed above is done using spreadsheets but it will soon be supported by the SCKAN Composer tool.

Criteria:

- Make sure you record sentence number from which the connectivity statements are derived.
- It will be a one to many relationship in most cases.
- Create a supplementary document to record all the sources, text extracts and data/figures used to draft the proposed populations. This significantly facilitates the interactive review process and the fact checking of the proposed populations by the expert(s).
- See [Official SCKAN NLP curation spreadsheet](#) for format and information that should be recorded for each proposed population

Identifying and naming neuron populations

1. Record the sentence number on which the population is based
 - a. The sentence may not be directly relevant to the neuron population described but we need this for bookkeeping
 - b. The sentence number is available from the list of statements provided to the curator
 - c. More than one neuron population can come from the same sentence
2. Assign the neuron population identifier of the form: NPO-(Your initials)-number, e.g., NPO-IZ-200
 - a. Each neuron population must have a unique identifier
3. Neuron population label should be of the form: Region A projects to Region B via Nerve C
 - a. Region A = soma location
 - b. Region B = Axon terminal location
 - c. Nerve C = Axon location
 - d. If the axon follows more than one nerve branch, please list them in order if known

A	B	C
Sentence ID	Neuron Population ID	Neuron population label (A to B via C)
3711	NPO-MM-01	Superior cervical ganglion to lacrimal gland via internal carotid nerve plexus via deep petrosal nerve via nerve of pterygoid canal via zygomatic branch of V2 via communicating branch of V1 via lacrimal branch of V1

[Official SCKAN NLP curation spreadsheet](#)

B	
Sentence ID	Sentence
Sentence ID: 3711	The motor fibres of the phrenic nerve innervate a group of lower motor neuron cells
Sentence ID: 3732	Respiratory gating of phrenic motor neurons
Sentence ID: 3878	Distribution of enteric nerve cells

Handling the elements of the NPO statement form

The form of neuronal population **Region A to Region B via Nerve C** is a useful tool, easily reviewed by field expert, annotated, coded and added into SCKAN. Here are some rules to handle each segment of the statement form.

Region A

- Stay consistent with what is clearly stated-proven in papers.

Region B

- A population can have multiple destinations that can be linked with “OR”.
 - e.g., **intramural ganglia of the kidney** to **renal artery** OR **lower ureter** via **postganglionic parasympathetic fiber**
- While using multiple sources to draft a population it is not easy to tell from the data whether there is only one or more populations innervating a region (i.e. parasympathetic innervation of the prostate). If the routing A and via C are the same we advice to create branches of the same population innervating the same structure (i.e. A to smooth muscle of prostate or blood vessel of the prostate via C).
- Note that these neuron populations are theoretical in that we do not model identified cell types. If a population projects to more than one target, we do not distinguish whether it is via axon collaterals or separate cell types.

Region C

- Indicate routes through nerve branches connected *in series* using “VIA”
 - e.g., **intermediolateral cell column of T12-L1** to **celiac-superior mesenteric ganglion complex** or **suprarenal ganglia** VIA **white rami communicantes** VIA **celiac nerve plexus**
- Indicate routes through branches that are connected in parallel using “OR”
 - **T4–L2 intermediolateral cell columns** to **prevertebral sympathetic ganglia in abdominal aortic plexus** via **greater** OR **lesser splanchnic nerve**

All segments

- Stay consistent with what is clearly stated-proven in papers. Naming of anatomical locations should be used as stated in the source. Naming and ontology alignment can occur later after consulting with SAWG/field expert.
- During distillation and drafting of a neuronal population there is the freedom to make an educated guess for a missing part (i.e. the nerve a preganglionic population uses to travel to a prevertebral ganglion from the spinal cord). At the stage of the drafting of the populations this is possible, however, this part that is not supported by a source should be annotated as such and brought for evaluation by the experts. If approved and the population is added to SCKAN this can be added to the notes of the population.

Handling Forward Connections and Use Case

NPO allows us to create the relation “**Forward Connection**” between two or more populations. In this way we can link a preganglionic population to a postganglionic. This relation can be added directly to the spreadsheets (see slides later).

Use Case:

The use case below is a great example of the modeling choices made when drafting populations. Populations A and B are both preganglionic populations that arise from the same origin (T12-L4 spinal cord). However, this population synapses both to paravertebral sympathetic chain and multiple prevertebral ganglia. Because of this reason we need to model this population into two separate ones as the routing is different and this cannot be supported by the partial order.

In the example below C is a forward connection to A and D is a forward connection to B.

Region A to Region B via Nerve C

A: T12-L4 spinal cord to paravertebral sympathetic chain of T12-L3 via white rami communicating rami of T12-L4

B: T12-L4 spinal cord to superior mesenteric ganglia OR renal nerve plexus ganglion via least splanchnic nerve OR lumbar splanchnic nerve

C: paravertebral sympathetic chain of T12-L3 to kidney via least splanchnic nerve OR lumbar splanchnic nerve via renal nerve

D: superior mesenteric ganglia OR renal nerve plexus ganglion to kidney via renal nerve

Population preparation for NPO after approval

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
NLP-ID	ID	Neuron population label (A to B via C)	Type	Structure	Identifier	Relationship	Axonal course poset
NPO-IZ-138	138	intramural ganglia of the kidney to renal artery OR to lower ureter via postganglionic fiber	Parasympathetic post-ganglionic	intramural ganglion of the kidney	http://uri.interlex.org/base/ilx_0795056	Soma	1
NPO-IZ-138	138			renal artery	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0001184	Axon terminal	3
NPO-IZ-138	138			lower ureter	http://uri.interlex.org/base/ilx_0795055	Axon terminal	3
NPO-IZ-138	138			postganglionic parasympathetic fiber	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0011929	Axon	2
NPO-IZ-138	138				http://uri.interlex.org/tqbuqs/uris/readable/neuron-	hasAnatomicalSystemPhenotype	
NPO-IZ-138	138				http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_9606	hasInstanceInTaxon	

The screenshot is an example of the NPO modeling of a population in a spreadsheet after it is approved by SAWG/field expert.

In columns A and B we add the full ID of the population and the integer ID respectively. For machine readability reasons both fields should be added for each row the coding of the population takes (in this case 6 rows).

Once the population is approved and in final version, all structures of the population in column C are extracted in column E under *Structure* and their unique identifiers are added (in column F). We can add only UBERON and Interlex IDs and use their preferred terms. There is a process of creating, reviewing and adding new anatomical terms on Interlex after being approved by SAWG/field expert. For the established workflow of suggesting new anatomical terms see documentation [here](#) and [here](#).

In column G we add the *Relationship* of each label. *Soma*, *Axon*, *Axon terminal* are added for A, C and B respectively. For the relation *hasAnatomicalSystemPhenotype* the URI for the parasympathetic postganglionic neuron phenotype is added and for *hasInstanceInTaxon* the URI for the NCBI taxonomy for humans in this case.

In column H is the partial order of this population. In autonomic populations number one is always the soma. In case of multiple origins the partial order numeration is always 1. The axon comes next. If there are multiple via there are two ways to encode the partial order. If it is a in series *via...via* then the numeration of the partial order is consecutive 2..3..4 etc. If vias are different branches separated by *OR* then the partial order should be the same integer (in this case 2). The destination is the end point and it is the last number and all destinations have the same integer.

Population preparation for NPO after approval

F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
Structure	Identifier	Relationship	Axonal	Observed i	Species diff	explicit complement	Alert Note
T10 spinal cord	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0006466	Soma	1	Human	Sex differenc		Alert: The spinal levels T10-L1 are mentioned in the references below as the sympathetic innervation of the female reproductive system arises
T11 spinal cord	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0006467	Soma	1				
T12 spinal cord	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0006468	Soma	1				
L1 spinal cord	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0006448	Soma	1				
pelvic ganglion	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0016508	Axon terminal	5				
superior hypogastric plexus	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0002013	Axon	2				
hypogastric nerve	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0005303	Axon	3				
inferior hypogastric nerve plexus	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0002014	Axon	4				
	http://uri.interlex.org/tbugs/uris/readable/neuron-phenotype-svm-pre	hasAnatomicalSystemPhenot...					
	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_9606	hasInstanceInTaxon					
	67	hasForwardConnectionPheno...					
	68	hasForwardConnectionPheno...					
	69	hasForwardConnectionPheno...					
	70	hasForwardConnectionPheno...					
	71	hasForwardConnectionPheno...					
	72	hasForwardConnectionPheno...					
	82	hasForwardConnectionPheno...					
	83	hasForwardConnectionPheno...					
	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/PATO_0000383	hasBiologicalSex					

This is a great example of the NPO modeling of a population that has multiple “Forward Connections”. This is modeled with the addition of the relation “*hasForwardConnectionPhenotype*” in column H and the addition of the relation “*hasBiologicalSex*” with the URI for the female ontology since this connection is describing the innervation of the female reproductive system, not present in males. As an identifier of the relation “*hasForwardConnectionPhenotype*” one should add the ID of the populations that are the forward connections (present in column B). In columns I and J one can import information about the species this population is observed in and the kind of species difference which in this case is “Sex difference”. Moreover, in this example you also see an example of an alert note added to this population in column M.

Quality Check before conversion to NPO

- Make sure that the labels are correctly translated into soma, axon terminal and nerve
- Make sure that the identifiers match the term
- Make sure identifiers are only UBERON or ILX
- Make sure any ILX identifiers have a parent of **Anatomical entity** or **nerve** or **nerve plexus**
- Make sure that the labels match the **preferred term** in UBERON or Interlex
 - Exceptions may be made for preferred labels which are very long and cumbersome provided that the meaning of the non-preferred term is unambiguous
 - Exceptions will also be made for species specific connections where the preferred terminology is different across species, e.g., inferior hypogastric nerve plexus in human vs pelvic ganglion in rodent.
 - Consult with SAWG or other field experts as needed on labels as necessary
- Make sure any common synonyms are added to Interlex

Curation and Review Annotations

When a set of populations is ready to be imported into SCKAN and the review process has been concluded one should add the following predicates:

1. In case the reviewer (field expert) has actively changed the population and has made suggestions that revised the population add the annotation **[Expert consultation: Expert's full name, ORCID]** in column G.
2. In case the populations has been reviewed and accepted by SAWG/field expert but no active feedback changed the population add predicate **[Expert review: SAWG]** in column G.
3. Add the annotation **[Curator's full name, ORCID]** for the curator in column V.

Curators should structure their notes in the official spreadsheet in a formal way in case these need to be surfaced.

Additional curatorial instructions for draft to NPO

- To make the knowledge engineering process more manageable, it is better to work with small sets of neuron populations rather than wait to create a complete set of projections for a given organ or circuit
- Once a set of projections have been identified, create a set of proposed neuron populations on a new tab or spreadsheet
 - Review population with SAWG or other field expert; make any recommended deletions or additions. Keep notes of feedback and track changes. Some information might need to make it to Alerts or Curation Notes and be surfaced in SCKAN.
 - Close the set by changing the color of the **column B [NLP-ID]** in Google sheets to **red**. Do NOT add any new populations after this point. If you identify additional populations, add them to another set.
 - Complete naming and QC process outlined in the following slides. Once complete, change the tab color to **yellow** to indicate that it is ready for full knowledge engineering.
 - Once KE is complete, change the color to **green** to indicate that these neurons have been added to the knowledge base.

Note: These instructions will become obsolete once SCKAN Composer is the main curatorial tool (see below)

Modeling of sensory populations

The form of sensory population is not the same with the autonomic connections “Region A to Region B via Nerve C”. We can break it down in two parts: 1) It starts from the soma, next indicates where its axon sensory terminal goes via the axon that is traveling with and 2) indicates where the axon terminal of the neuron goes via the axon that is traveling with.

The modeling for sensory populations is:

Soma “S” with axon sensory terminal in “T” via “X” with axon terminal in “Y” via “Z”

A	B	C	D
R	ID	Neuron population label (A to B via C)	Type
NPO-IZ-114	114	left nodose ganglion with axon sensory terminal in hilus of the liver OR bile duct OR portal vein via anterior abdominal vagal trunk with axon terminal in nucleus of solitary tract via vagus nerve	Sensory
NPO-IZ-114	114		

Here is an example of a sensory population.

Soma: left nodose ganglion

With axon sensory terminal in: hilus of the liver OR bile duct OR portal vein (as it has multiple branches).

Via (from the soma to the axon sensory terminal): anterior abdominal vagal trunk
With axon terminal in: nucleus of solitary tract

Via (from the soma to the axon terminal): vagus nerve

Modeling of sensory populations

E	F	G	H	I
Structure	Identifier	Relationship	Axonal course poset	Observed in species
left nodose ganglion	http://uri.interlex.org/base/ilx_0790316	Soma	3	Rat
hilar portion of hepatic duct	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0015423	Axon sensory terminal	1	
bile duct	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0002394	Axon sensory terminal	1	
portal vein	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0002017	Axon sensory terminal	1	
nucleus of solitary tract	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0009050	Axon terminal	5	
anterior abdominal vagal trunk	http://uri.interlex.org/base/ilx_0793826	Axon-Leading-To-Sensory-Terminal	2	
vagus nerve	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0001759	Axon	4	
	http://uri.interlex.org/tqbuqs/uris/readable/SensoryPhenotype	hasCircuitRole		
	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_10116	hasInstanceInTaxon		

The modeling into NPO is similar with the autonomic populations described above. The correct label is added in column E under *Structure* and the unique identifier for each anatomical location in column F.

There are a couple of unique relations added for sensory populations 1) is the relation “*Axon-Leading-To-Sensory-Terminal*” for the axon originating from the soma leading to the axon sensory terminal and the relations “*hasCircuitRole*”, which is the URI for the sensory phenotype.

The partial order of the sensory populations in column H, under *Axonal course poset* follow the information flow. Number 1 starts from the “*axon sensory terminal*” leading via the “*Axon-Leading-To-Sensory-Terminal*” to the soma and from there the “*axon*” leads to the “*axon terminal*” of the neuron.

Updates of content of SCKAN

Our primary objective when populating SCKAN was to achieve the broadest possible coverage of neuronal populations innervating diverse systems. The long-term goal is to continually enrich SCKAN with new populations and corroborate or expand its existing knowledge base using newly published research.

The addition of new neuronal populations adheres to the curation workflow outlined earlier. A key scenario involves new research supporting existing populations in SCKAN. In such cases, and following the criteria detailed below, the addition of a predicate citing the new research is sufficient, provided the new data undergoes rigorous evaluation in the context of SCKAN's existing knowledge.

Two more complex yet significant scenarios involve updating SCKAN content:

1. When new information complements an existing SCKAN population.
2. When new information contradicts the knowledge currently in SCKAN.

In both cases, it is crucial to determine whether the new information pertains to the existing population in SCKAN. This requires a careful review of the original evidence that informed the published SCKAN population, alongside the new data, in collaboration with field experts. Such thorough evaluation ensures accurate disambiguation and proper integration of new information into the knowledge base. Therefore, maintaining detailed records of all sources, figures, and text extracts used in distilling and drafting connectivity statements, as previously discussed, is essential.

Criteria for updating an existing population:

- New information has to be same species
- New research should be have the same level of quality

Use case: New information added for only one population of the “Forward Connection”

You can see below the two original populations added in SCKAN in [black text](#). The two population represent the sympathetic innervation of the ovary in the rat. The postganglionic population 38 is the “Forward Connection” of the preganglionic population 39.

Both populations were added to SCKAN following the distillation and evaluation of sources with a field expert. The population was accompanied by predicates supporting the evidence.

More recently it came to our attention a recent paper (not included in the primary distillation).

The newly published information was evaluated based on species and research method and the new anatomical entities added are seen in [red text](#).

NPO-IZ-39 (Symp preganglionic): T9-T10 spinal cord to celiac ganglion-superior mesenteric ganglion complex via greater splanchnic nerve

NPO-IZ-38 (Symp postganglionic): celiac ganglion-superior mesenteric ganglion complex OR [suprarenal ganglion](#) to left ovary via superior ovarian nerve OR [ovarian plexus nerve](#)

Suprarenal ganglion
does affect preganglionic

OPN doesn't affect
preganglionic

However, there are several issues arising after the addition of the new anatomical locations.

1. The addition of the “suprarenal ganglion” affects the “hasForwardConnection” phenotype as the model will assume automatically a relationship between synapse points of populations 38 and 39 even if it is simply implied. The only information that is confirmed is that CSMG complex is the synapse point that links the two populations together. To avoid faulty generated relationships where there is no evidence we decided to split the population 38 into two populations (38 and 38-1, see next slide). This had to be documented with the addition of an Alert in the curator spreadsheet and curator notes. In the future, in the light of evidence suggesting population 39 also synapses in the suprarenal ganglion populations 38 and 38-1 can be merged and annotated accordingly. The 38-1 was not added as a Forward Connection to 39.
2. The addition of the “ovarian plexus nerve” in population 38 does not affect the Forward Connection relationship. After splitting the population into 38 and 38-1 we had to keep the OPN anatomical location as indicated by the most recent evidence. This has to be documented as an “Alert” in the alert notes by keeping in details the date, the changes and the reason. With the current workflows with each next SCKAN release an updated populations will be overwritten and the changes can be tracked from the Alerts notes.

Use case: New information added for only one population of the “Forward Connection”

You can see below the final populations after the updates and the decision to split population 38.

NPO-IZ-39 (Symp preganglionic): T9-T10 spinal cord to celiac ganglion-superior mesenteric ganglion complex via greater splanchnic nerve

[Maintained relationship “hasForwardConnection”: **NPO-IZ-38**]

NPO-IZ-38 (Symp postganglionic): celiac ganglion-superior mesenteric ganglion complex to left ovary via superior ovarian nerve OR ovarian plexus nerve

NPO-IZ-38-1 (Symp postganglionic): suprarenal ganglion to left ovary via superior ovarian nerve OR ovarian plexus nerve

Set of tools leveraged for current curation workflow

The curation workflow leveraged a comprehensive set of tools to ensure accuracy and consistency throughout the process. These included literature distillation and evaluation with field experts, the integration of data into SCKAN, and the assignment of supporting predicates to provide robust evidence. Together, these tools facilitated the creation of a precise and reliable representation of neuronal populations within the knowledge graph.

Tools employed:

- **OSCAP (The Open SAWG Connectivity Authoring Pipeline)**
- **Google docs:** for collaborative information distillation, directly supports with sorted information in the edits and experts' feedback.
- **Google spreadsheets:** Supports the drafting and modeling of neuronal populations in NPO efficiently.
- **Neuron Phenotype Ontology (NPO):** Gillespie et al., (2022) The Neuron Phenotype Ontology: A FAIR Approach to Proposing and Classifying Neuronal Types 10.1007/s12021-022-09566-7

Future SCKAN Curation Workflow

The SCKAN Composer is the unifying tool where new content from the NLP pipeline is triaged, knowledge distilled, reviewed by field experts and eventually modeled in NPO and exported directly into SCKAN. See below the updated SCKAN curation workflow after the transition to Composer and how many of the steps will be taking place directly in Composer.

Current workflow

Neuron Population Curation			
TRIAGE	1	Monthly NLP screening of literature	
	2	Import into OSCAP	
	3	Triage statements	
	4	Consult with subject matter experts	
	5	OSCAP status updated	
DISTILL	6	Forward statements and notes to curator	
	7	Create neuron population statements	
	8	Subject matter expert review	
	9	OSCAP status update	
	10	Model approved populations in NPO	
ENGINEER	11	QC NPO populations	
	12	Knowledge Engineer converts into NPO	
	13	Import into SCKAN	
	14	Final subject matter expert review	
	15	OSCAP status update	

SCKAN Composer

Neuron Population Curation			
TRIAGE	1	Monthly NLP screening of literature	
	2	Composer Import	
	3	Triage statements	
	4	Domain expert review	
DISTILL	5	Create neuron population statements	
	6	Domain expert review	
	7	Model approved populations	
	8	Final domain expert review	
ENGINEER	9	QC NPO populations	
	10	Composer Export and SCKAN Import	

SCKAN Composer allows an interactive triage process

The screenshot displays the SCKAN Composer interface. On the left, a sidebar contains navigation options: 'Manage', 'Sentences List' (selected), and 'Statements List'. The main area is titled 'Sentences List' and shows '811 sentences in total'. A search bar is present with the placeholder text 'Search for Sentences'. Below the search bar is a table of sentences. A green box highlights the table, and a red box highlights the 'Filters' sidebar on the right.

ID	Sentence	Status	Last edited	Owner	Tags
591	15, 19 The chorda tympani nerve arises from the most distal mastoid segment and crosses the tympanic cavity to join the lingual nerve,...	Open	18 December 2024 11:38 pm	Ilias Ziogas	
42	1) There are three cervical ganglions: the superior cervical ganglion at the C2 level, the middle cervical ganglion at the C5-C6 level and...	Compose Later	19 November 2024 5:48 pm	Ilias Ziogas	Anatomy res...
163	In 10 % there were indirect connections with a distinct phrenic nerve branch joining the celiac ganglion , from which celiac plexus...	Compose Later	30 October 2024 9:54 pm	Ilias Ziogas	
10	First described by the German anatomist Hubert von Luschka in 1850, the sinuvertebral nerve has since acquired many other name...	Needs Further Review	30 October 2024 9:54 pm	Ilias Ziogas	HubMAP
170	Presynaptic inhibition of acetylcholine release via GABAB receptors occurs at lumbar preganglionic splanchnic nerves synapsing withi...	Compose Later	30 October 2024 9:53 pm	Ilias Ziogas	Uncertain V...
346	It is well known that the ovary obtains motor innervation both from the sympathetic system (preganglionic efferent perikarya are...	Open	30 October 2024 9:45 pm	Ilias Ziogas	FemRep, Ili...
122	Consistent with a role for the vagus in the regulation of the L cell , stimulation of the distal end of the celiac branch of the...	Compose Later	30 October 2024 9:37 pm	Ilias Ziogas	HubMAP, A...
185	As capsaicin also induces parasympathetic relaxant reflexes in the airways (Mazzone & Canning, 2002a,b,c), we cut the vagus nerve...	Compose Later	30 October 2024 8:06 pm	Ilias Ziogas	Compare with
82	As [3H]leucine labelling of nerve fibres is the result of anterograde transport exclusively , it can be concluded that trigeminal nerve...	Compose Later	28 October 2024 6:13 pm	Ilias Ziogas	Cranial, Eye
398	celiac-mesenteric ganglion to ovary via superior ovarian nerve created from neurons on 2024-02-19 15:50:06	Compose Now	20 September 2024 3:38 pm	Ilias Ziogas	

The 'Filters' sidebar on the right is titled 'Filters' and contains the text 'Apply filters to the sentences list'. It has a close button (X) in the top right corner. The 'Status' section includes the following options:

- Completed
- Compose Later
- Compose Now
- Excluded
- Needs Further Review
- Open
- Ready To Compose

The 'Tags' section includes the following options:

- 20241005 SFIN
- Accupoints
- Add citation
- ALERT
- ALERT - species
- ALERT - spinal segmental routing visualization
- Anatomy resource
- Cardiovascular system
- Compare with KB
- ComposerBug
- Connection to add
- Cranial
- Dataset DOI
- Direct Experimental Evidence

Composer offers an interactive triage process. You see a list of sentences extracted with the NLP-based pipeline (green). Working independently on each record you can use tags, add notes and move the record forward with a variety of stages highlighted in red. One can filter based on tags and/or status and can search through records using the search function.

SCKAN Composer allows a faster, less error-prone curation process

Sentence Details #346 [Open](#) Needs further review

Last Edited on 30 October 2024, 30/10/2024, 9:45 pm

Knowledge Statements Check for duplicates

Statement 83

NPO-IZ-57: nucleus tractus solitarius to nodose ganglion via preganglionic nerve

Enter Provenances (Press Enter to add a Provenance)

^ Statement Details

Species

rat x Select Species

Phenotype

parasympathetic pre-ganglionic

Projection phenotype

Enter Projection Phenotype

Laterality

Enter Laterality

SCKAN Composer allows a faster, less error-prone curation process. In the screenshot appears part of the distillation process where one drafts the neuronal population in the green highlighted area and adds the provenances below the connectivity statement. Highlighted in red you see a list of connectivity statement details where you fill in phenotypes such as species, sex, circuit type etc. There are fields that allow you to keep additional notes where one can keep text extracts and sources used to draft the connectivity statement. The drafting process includes also the curation notes and all the sources. This process can also take place using spreadsheets and google docs as long as they are linked in the notes of the record in Composer.

SCKAN Composer allows a faster, less error-prone curation process

Statement Details #265

ExportedCompose now

Last Edited on 21 December 2024, 21/12/2024, 12:40 am

Distillation Proofing

Knowledge Statement

Check for duplicates

Statement Preview

In human, the sympathetic pre-ganglionic connection goes from Intermediolateral nucleus of first lumbar segment or Intermediolateral nucleus of second lumbar segment to inferior mesenteric ganglion or prevertebral sympathetic ganglion in abdominal aortic plexus via lumbar splanchnic nerve.

This connection projects from the Intermediolateral nucleus of first lumbar segment and Intermediolateral nucleus of second lumbar segment.

This neuron population connects to connectivity statement with id: [267](#).

intermediolateral columns of L1-L2 to abdominal aortic or inferior mesenteric plexus ganglia via lumbar splanchnic nerves

Once the statement is created the review process takes place directly in SCKAN Composer, with the field experts leaving their feedback in the comments. In the screenshot you see the unique ID of the statement generated (#265) and a statement preview automatically generated with all the information imported during the distillation process, highlighted in red.

SCKAN Composer allows a faster, less error-prone modeling process

Path Builder

Origin

Soma

Via

Axon

Via

From

Destination

Axon terminal From

Axon terminal From

Forward connection(s)

[abdominal aortic or inferior mesenteric plexus ganglion to distal one-third of the transverse colon or descending colon or sigmoid colon or rectum or upper part of the anal canal via inferior mesenteric nerve plexus](#)

SCKAN Composer offers the possibility to model the approved neuronal populations directly on the platform. In the screenshot you see the elements of the NPO form **A to B via C**, Soma, Destination and Axon (via). In each field you can add the anatomical location by searching from the list. You can also indicate **from** which element comes from (e.g. The axon terminal “inferior mesenteric ganglion” comes from the “lumbar splanchnic nerve”). In the example above there is only one axon. In the presence of more than one, the **From** feature would allow one to create the partial order of the population as needed.

SCKAN Composer allows a faster, less error-prone modeling process

In the *Statement Display* that SCKAN Composer offers you can see in real time the visual representation of the population that is being modeled. This feature is interactive giving the possibility to play around with each element of the neuron and change the layout as needed.